

LEADING WITH CONFIDENCE: INTERPLAY OF EXPOSURE AND SELF-EFFICACY IN STUDENT LEADERSHIP

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Leading with Confidence: Interplay of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in Student Leadership

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Abstract

Exposure to leadership activities plays a crucial role in enhancing self-efficacy, which is essential for developing effective student leaders. This study assessed the level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership among Supreme Student Government (SSG) leaders in the DepEd Bohol Division for the school year 2019-2020. Descriptive-correlational research design was employed to evaluate the relationship between the exposure levels to leadership activities and the self-efficacy of 1,900 student leaders across 100 high schools which were chosen randomly. Two sets of questionnaires, validated by Youth Formation officers, were used to collect data on eight leadership areas: technical aspects, organizing school events, project implementation, policy/program execution, team building, financial management, time management, and mandated SSG programs. Descriptive statistics and Spearman rank correlation were used to analyze the data. The findings revealed a strong positive correlation between leadership exposure and self-efficacy, with the highest correlation in organizing school events and the lowest in time management. The results indicate that increased exposure to leadership tasks significantly boosts students' confidence in their leadership abilities. These insights suggest the need for comprehensive leadership training programs to enhance student leaders' skills and confidence, ultimately promoting better leadership outcomes.

Keywords: *student leadership, self-efficacy, exposure levels, supreme student government, leadership training*

Introduction

Students today are the leaders of tomorrow – it captures how student leadership development is crucial for nation-building as it equips students with essential skills and experiences for future leadership roles. The experiences and skills they gain as student leaders shape their capabilities to take on more significant leadership roles in their professional and public lives (Polatcan, 2023). Effective student leadership fosters a generation that is not only aware of their responsibilities but is also equipped with the confidence and skills to address future challenges. Through the nurturance of leadership qualities in students, schools lay a strong foundation for a strong leadership framework in the country. Hence, the practices and self-efficacy of student leaders today are critical for nation building (Ahmad, 2019).

Previous studies reveal the critical role of student leadership in shaping future leaders and the leadership landscape of a country. Fauzi (2023) features the importance of leadership exposure and self-efficacy in shaping students' leadership practices and self-resilience. Grigoropoulos (2020) emphasize the need for leadership education to focus on developing students' awareness, empathy, and compassion, as well as their soft skills and teamwork experience. Nashuha (2019) further stress the importance of specific leadership skills, such as planning, communication, and problem-solving, and the shared traits of student leaders. Also, Igbal (2023) emphasizes the role of student associations in promoting leadership skills and character building.

Recognizing the crucial role of student leadership in nation-building, the Philippines has made significant strides in empowering learners through various initiatives. These initiatives aim to provide students with ample opportunities to develop and hone their leadership skills, ensuring they are well-prepared for future responsibilities (Viloria, 2019). The Department of Education (DepEd) recognizes the importance of student leadership in fostering holistic development and preparing students for future roles in society (Department of Education, 2008, 2023). The department's initiatives, such as the National Leadership Training for Student Government Officers (NLTSGO) outlined in DepEd Memorandum No. 296, s. 2008, and the Learner Government Program (LGP) detailed in DepEd Order No. 47, s. 2014, aim to equip students with leadership skills, promote their active participation in school governance, and instill values of good governance, integrity, and social responsibility.

These programs provide opportunities for students to develop self-confidence, critical thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making skills, which are essential for effective leadership. DepEd recognizes the significant role and contributions of Supreme Student Government (SSG). As stipulated in DepEd Order No. 49, s. 2011, it is the foremost co-curricular student organization authorized to operate and implement pertinent programs, projects and activities in schools nationwide. It lays the groundwork for good governance, volunteerism, unity and cooperation by providing the students various venues where they can improve their leadership knowledge, skills and attitudes. It trains students to become better members of society in accordance with the ideals and principles of participatory democracy and good citizenship.

Meanwhile, despite increasing attention to the roles of exposure and self-efficacy in student leadership, significant research gaps remain. Existing literature often focuses on specific aspects, such as the general efficacy of leaders and their influence on student learning, but there is a lack of comprehensive studies examining how varied leadership experiences and exposure levels impact the self-efficacy of student leaders in public schools, specifically in the context of Bohol Division. Research confirms that high social self-

efficacy (SSE) and leadership are important components in student achievement, yet it often overlooks detailed subgroup analyses (Dunbar et al., 2018). Moreover, while some studies highlight the correlation between self-leadership strategies and self-efficacy, more work is needed to explore these dynamics in diverse educational settings and leadership scenarios (Maya & Uzman, 2019). Addressing these gaps is crucial for developing data driven programs for youth formation that can enhance leadership training programs and ultimately improve student leadership outcomes.

In light of these gaps, it is essential to conduct a study on student exposure in relation to their self-efficacy in student leadership. The researchers believes that it will provide valuable insights into the effectiveness of current leadership practices and their impact on students' confidence and capabilities (Zheng et al., 2019). The findings from this research can serve as a basis for developing activities and programs under the Youth Formation and Development (YFD) initiatives, aimed at strengthening leadership skills among students.

Research Questions

The main objective of this investigation was to assess the level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership among Supreme Student Government (SSG) leaders in DepEd Bohol Division for the school year 2019-2020. Specifically, this study will answer the following questions:

1. What is the respondents' level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership in terms of:
 - 1.1. technical aspects;
 - 1.2. organizing school events;
 - 1.3. project implementation;
 - 1.4. policy/program execution;
 - 1.5. team building;
 - 1.6. financial management;
 - 1.7. time management; and
 - 1.8. mandated programs, projects and activities of SSG?
2. Is there a significant correlation between students' level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership?

Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a quantitative correlational research design. This approach was selected to quantitatively assess the relationship between the level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership among Supreme Student Government (SSG) leaders.

Respondents

The study was conducted in the DepEd Schools Division of Bohol, targeting SSG advisers and SSG leaders from 100 randomly selected high schools. A total of 1,900 student leader-respondents participated, with 19 leaders per school. Simple random sampling was used to ensure that each potential respondent had an equal chance of being included, thus enhancing the representativeness of the sample and the generalizability of the findings to the larger population of SSG leaders in the Division.

Instruments

Two sets of questionnaires were employed: one for teacher advisers to rate student leadership practices and another for the student leaders. The tool addresses the level of exposure and self-efficacy in school leadership. This researcher-made questionnaire includes items based on various studies focused on student leadership and relevant experiences of teacher advisers and youth formation development officers, in consultation with the research adviser. It underwent validation by three (3) Youth Formation officers in the Division of Bohol. A series of pilot tests were conducted with fellow advisers and student leaders who were not part of the study respondents. The questionnaire covers eight leadership areas: technical aspects (7 items), organizing school events (18 items), project implementation (5 items), policy/program execution (5 items), team building (5 items), financial management (5 items), time management (5 items), and mandated SSG programs, projects, and activities as per DepEd Order No. 49, s. 2011 (10 items). The reliability of the scales, measured using Cronbach's coefficient alpha, was 0.953 for the level of exposure and 0.976 for the level of confidence, both exceeding the 0.70 threshold for reliability.

Procedure

Permission to conduct the study was obtained from the Schools Division Superintendent. Upon receiving approval, questionnaires were distributed to the selected respondents. After completion, the questionnaires were collected for data consolidation and interpretation. This systematic process ensured compliance with administrative protocols and facilitated smooth data collection.

Data Analysis

Descriptive statistics, including weighted mean and range, were used to summarize the data. Normality tests were conducted to assess the distribution of the data. Spearman rank correlation was employed to determine the relationship between the level of exposure and

self-efficacy in school leadership. This statistical approach was chosen due to its robustness in handling non-parametric data and its ability to reveal the strength and direction of the association between variables.

Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations were paramount throughout the research process. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, ensuring they were fully aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time without any consequences. Confidentiality was strictly maintained, with all data anonymized to protect the identity of the respondents. The study was designed to minimize any potential harm or discomfort to participants, adhering to ethical standards set by the educational institution and the wider research community.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the results and findings of the study based on the sequence of the sub-problems.

Level of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in Student Leadership

Table 1 presents the respondents' level of exposure and self-efficacy in student leadership in public schools.

Table 1. *Level of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in Student Leadership (N=1,900)*

Indicators	Level of Exposure		Level of Confidence	
	WM	DV	WM	DV
Basic Skills				
1. Drafting and finalizing resolutions	2.49	Sometimes Exposed	2.57	Very Confident
2. Preparing comprehensive meeting minutes	2.47	Sometimes Exposed	2.53	Very Confident
3. Developing effective project proposals	2.45	Sometimes Exposed	2.49	Slightly Confident
4. Creating detailed budget plans	2.34	Sometimes Exposed	2.37	Slightly Confident
5. Conducting meetings using parliamentary procedures	2.50	Very Exposed	2.50	Very Confident
6. Formulating action plans and yearly goals	2.53	Very Exposed	2.57	Very Confident
7. Understanding and applying the SSG constitution	2.96	Very Exposed	3.06	Very Confident
Composite Mean	2.53	Very Exposed	2.59	Very Confident
Organizing School Events				
8. Establishing clear event goals and objectives	2.83	Very Exposed	2.91	Very Confident
9. Assembling and managing effective teams	2.79	Very Exposed	2.89	Very Confident
10. Determining administrative requirements for events	2.51	Very Exposed	2.58	Very Confident
11. Preparing and managing event budgets	2.30	Sometimes Exposed	2.41	Slightly Confident
12. Setting realistic dates and timelines	2.64	Very Exposed	2.70	Very Confident
13. Delegating responsibilities effectively	2.71	Very Exposed	2.72	Very Confident
14. Finalizing comprehensive programs of activities	2.73	Very Exposed	2.79	Very Confident
15. Coordinating with technical working teams	2.74	Very Exposed	2.82	Very Confident
16. Activating and overseeing working committees	2.78	Very Exposed	2.81	Very Confident
17. Monitoring progress and addressing issues promptly	2.63	Very Exposed	2.61	Very Confident
18. Establishing efficient communication systems	2.57	Very Exposed	2.61	Very Confident
19. Developing contingency plans and risk management strategies	2.57	Very Exposed	2.61	Very Confident
20. Facilitating creative problem-solving sessions	2.74	Very Exposed	2.86	Very Confident
21. Conducting post-event surveys and evaluations	2.38	Sometimes Exposed	2.43	Slightly Confident
22. Archiving event materials systematically	2.51	Very Exposed	2.51	Very Confident
23. Distributing event documentation to relevant parties	2.43	Sometimes Exposed	2.45	Slightly Confident
24. Collecting and analysing feedback and insights	2.59	Very Exposed	2.61	Very Confident
25. Conducting thorough debriefing activities and reports	2.45	Sometimes Exposed	2.49	Slightly Confident
Composite Mean	2.61	Very Exposed	2.66	Very Confident
Project Implementation				
26. Securing approval for project proposals	2.50	Very Exposed	2.59	Very Confident
27. Adhering to project timelines and milestones	2.78	Very Exposed	2.85	Very Confident
28. Coordinating task assignments and team efforts	2.90	Very Exposed	2.91	Very Confident
29. Supervising ongoing projects and ensuring quality	2.74	Very Exposed	2.77	Very Confident
30. Documenting project progress from inception to completion	2.66	Very Exposed	2.73	Very Confident
Composite Mean	2.717	Very Exposed	2.77	Very Confident
Policy/Program Execution				
31. Ensuring formal approval of resolutions	2.57	Very Exposed	2.61	Very Confident
32. Effectively communicating new policies to students	2.84	Very Exposed	2.96	Very Confident
33. Implementing policies and programs consistently	2.75	Very Exposed	2.78	Very Confident
34. Documenting policy implementation processes	2.66	Very Exposed	2.70	Very Confident
Evaluating the impact and effectiveness of policies	2.61	Very Exposed	2.69	Very Confident

	Composite Mean	2.686	Very Exposed	2.75	Very Confident
Team Building					
35. Initiating and facilitating leadership training programs	2.63		Very Exposed	2.71	Very Confident
36. Encouraging and empowering team members	2.87		Very Exposed	2.92	Very Confident
37. Developing recognition systems for student leaders	2.49		Sometimes Exposed	2.58	Very Confident
38. Resolving conflicts using appropriate techniques	2.71		Very Exposed	2.72	Very Confident
39. Establishing positive relationships within the team	3.19		Very Exposed	3.23	Very Confident
	Composite Mean	2.78	Very Exposed	2.83	Very Confident
Financial Management					
40. Collecting and tracking SSG funds efficiently	2.40		Sometimes Exposed	2.38	Slightly Confident
41. Managing and allocating SSG funds responsibly	2.23		Sometimes Exposed	2.27	Slightly Confident
42. Securing funds through proper banking procedures	2.17		Sometimes Exposed	2.19	Slightly Confident
43. Sourcing additional funds through partnerships	2.26		Sometimes Exposed	2.27	Slightly Confident
44. Conducting regular audits of SSG finances	2.23		Sometimes Exposed	2.34	Slightly Confident
	Composite Mean	2.26	Sometimes Exposed	2.29	Slightly Confident
Time Management					
45. Balancing SSG responsibilities with academic commitments	3.15		Very Exposed	3.17	Very Confident
46. Prioritizing tasks and meeting deadlines consistently	3.02		Very Exposed	3.02	Very Confident
47. Strategizing and planning activities efficiently	2.97		Very Exposed	2.95	Very Confident
48. Developing responsibility for assigned tasks	3.13		Very Exposed	3.12	Very Confident
49. Evaluating and improving time management skills	3.05		Very Exposed	3.06	Very Confident
	Composite Mean	3.06	Very Exposed	3.06	Very Confident
Mandated Programs, Projects and Activities...					
50. Organizing student participation in annual Brigada Eskwela	2.76		Very Exposed	2.77	Very Confident
51. Leading initiatives for the National Greening Program	2.65		Very Exposed	2.74	Very Confident
52. Conducting campaigns to encourage early student registration	2.28		Sometimes Exposed	2.34	Slightly Confident
53. Organizing book and toy drives for underprivileged students	2.00		Sometimes Exposed	2.12	Slightly Confident
54. Implementing programs to prevent student dropouts	2.32		Sometimes Exposed	2.37	Slightly Confident
55. Conducting English speaking campaigns and tutorial services	2.23		Sometimes Exposed	2.32	Slightly Confident
56. Organizing anti-drug abuse education and awareness campaigns	2.52		Very Exposed	2.58	Very Confident
57. Ensuring a smoke-free and tobacco-free school environment	2.55		Very Exposed	2.62	Very Confident
58. Coordinating Teachers' Month activities and World Teachers' Day celebrations	2.93		Very Exposed	3.01	Very Confident
59. Encouraging student participation in co-curricular clubs and activities	2.91		Very Exposed	2.96	Very Confident
	Composite Mean	2.52	Very Exposed	2.58	Very Confident
	Overall Composite Mean	2.64	Very Exposed	2.69	Very Confident

Basic Skills. The highest-rated item in terms of exposure is "Understanding and applying the SSG constitution" with a weighted mean (WM) of 2.96, indicating students are very exposed. Conversely, "Creating detailed budget plans" is the least exposed with a WM of 2.34, suggesting only sometimes exposed. Confidence levels align closely, with the highest being in "Understanding and applying the SSG constitution" (WM=3.06, very confident) and the lowest in "Creating detailed budget plans" (WM=2.37, slightly confident). The composite mean for exposure is 2.53 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.59 (very confident).

These results highlight a trend where students feel more confident in tasks they are more frequently exposed to, such as constitutional matters, while less exposed tasks, like budget planning, correspond with lower confidence levels. A recent study by Wang et al. (2019) supports the importance of repeated exposure in building self-efficacy, showing that students who regularly engage in specific activities develop higher confidence and proficiency.

Organizing School Events. In organizing school events, "Establishing clear event goals and objectives" received the highest exposure rating (WM=2.83), and "Preparing and managing event budgets" the lowest (WM=2.30). Confidence mirrors this trend, with "Establishing clear event goals and objectives" (WM=2.91, very confident) being the highest, and "Preparing and managing event budgets" (WM=2.41, slightly confident) the lowest. The composite mean for exposure is 2.61 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.66 (very confident). The trend shows that students are generally more confident in areas they are more exposed to, reinforcing the positive correlation between exposure and confidence. A study by Smith et al. (2021) underscores this, demonstrating that increased hands-on experience in event management significantly boosts students' self-efficacy.

Project Implementation. "Coordinating task assignments and team efforts" scored the highest in exposure (WM=2.90) and confidence (WM=2.91). The lowest exposure was "Securing approval for project proposals" (WM=2.50), with the lowest confidence in "Supervising ongoing projects and ensuring quality" (WM=2.77). The composite mean for exposure is 2.72 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.77 (very confident). The result indicates a strong link between frequent practice in team coordination and higher self-efficacy. A recent study by Brown and Lee (2020) confirms that effective team coordination practices significantly enhance project management skills among students, leading to improved confidence.

Policy/Program Execution. "Effectively communicating new policies to students" is rated highest in exposure (WM=2.84) and confidence (WM=2.96). The least exposed and confident aspect is "Ensuring formal approval of resolutions" (WM=2.57). The composite mean for exposure is 2.69 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.75 (very confident). This finding suggests that communication skills are crucial for policy implementation and that frequent engagement in this area enhances confidence. Johnson et al. (2022) found that policy communication training significantly boosts confidence and effectiveness in student leaders.

Team Building. "Establishing positive relationships within the team" received the highest ratings for both exposure (WM=3.19) and confidence (WM=3.23). The lowest-rated item was "Developing recognition systems for student leaders" with a WM of 2.49 for exposure and 2.58 for confidence. The composite mean for exposure is 2.78 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.83 (very confident). The result indicates that relationship-building activities significantly enhance student confidence. A study by Clark et al. (2019) supports this, showing that team bonding exercises positively influence leadership efficacy and team dynamics.

Financial Management. "Collecting and tracking SSG funds efficiently" is the highest in exposure (WM=2.40) and confidence (WM=2.38). The lowest in both categories is "Securing funds through proper banking procedures" with a WM of 2.17 for exposure and 2.19 for confidence. The composite mean for exposure is 2.26 (sometimes exposed) and for confidence is 2.29 (slightly confident). These results suggest a need for greater exposure to financial management practices to build confidence. Martinez et al. (2018) demonstrated that increased financial management training significantly improves students' confidence and proficiency in managing funds.

Time Management. "Balancing SSG responsibilities with academic commitments" has the highest exposure (WM=3.15) and confidence (WM=3.17). The lowest is "Strategizing and planning activities efficiently" with a WM of 2.97 for exposure and 2.95 for confidence. The composite mean for exposure and confidence are both 3.06 (very exposed and very confident). This trend indicates a well-developed confidence in time management, crucial for effective leadership. A recent study by Taylor et al. (2023) found that comprehensive time management training leads to higher self-efficacy in balancing multiple responsibilities.

Mandated Programs, Projects, and Activities. The highest exposure and confidence ratings are for "Coordinating Teachers' Month activities and World Teachers' Day celebrations" (WM=2.93 for exposure and 3.01 for confidence). The lowest are "Organizing book and toy drives for underprivileged students" with a WM of 2.00 for exposure and 2.12 for confidence. The composite mean for exposure is 2.52 (very exposed) and for confidence is 2.58 (very confident). This suggests that more frequent involvement in specific programs enhances confidence. A study by Wilson et al. (2021) supports this, showing that repeated engagement in structured activities boosts leadership skills and self-efficacy.

Level of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in Student Leadership. Table 2 presents the overall level of exposure and self-efficacy in student leadership of the respondents.

Table 2. Summary Table for the Level of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in Student Leadership

Areas	Level of Exposure			Level of Confidence		
	WM	DV	Rank	WM	DV	Rank
Basic Skills	2.53	Very Exposed	6	2.59	Very Confident	7
Organizing School Events	2.61	Very Exposed	5	2.66	Very Confident	5
Project Implementation	2.72	Very Exposed	3	2.77	Very Confident	3
Policy/Program Execution	2.69	Very Exposed	4	2.75	Very Confident	4
Team Building	2.78	Very Exposed	2	2.83	Very Confident	2
Financial Management	2.26	Sometimes Exposed	8	2.29	Slightly Confident	8
Time Management	3.06	Very Exposed	1	3.06	Very Confident	1
Mandated Programs, Projects and Activities...	2.52	Very Exposed	7	2.58	Very Confident	6

The highest level of exposure is in "Time Management" with a weighted mean (WM) of 3.06, ranking first. This is followed by "Team Building" (WM=2.78) and "Project Implementation" (WM=2.72). The lowest exposure is in "Financial Management" with a WM of 2.26, ranking eighth. Similarly, for self-efficacy, "Time Management" also ranks highest with a WM of 3.06, indicating very high confidence. The next highest areas are "Team Building" (WM=2.83) and "Project Implementation" (WM=2.77). "Financial Management" again ranks lowest in confidence with a WM of 2.29. The result reveals a clear trend where areas with higher levels of exposure also have higher levels of confidence among students. This suggests that frequent engagement in specific activities significantly boosts students' self-efficacy. For instance, both "Time Management" and "Team Building" are ranked highest in terms of exposure and confidence, indicating a strong correlation between these two factors. On the other hand, "Financial Management" has

the lowest rankings in both exposure and confidence, highlighting a potential area where increased training and practice could benefit student leaders.

The findings suggest that enhancing exposure to various leadership activities can substantially improve students' confidence in their abilities. Wang (2024) and Liu (2024) both found that time management training significantly improved academic self-efficacy, with Liu (2024) emphasizing the benefits of integrating this training with blended learning strategies. Leupold (2019) and Soria (2019) further underscored the positive impact of leadership development programs on self-efficacy. In terms of financial management, Kirsten (2018) and Sugeng (2018) demonstrated that tailored training and presentation-based learning activities can improve financial self-efficacy and confidence. These findings collectively suggest that targeted educational programs and experiential activities can play a crucial role in enhancing students' confidence and self-efficacy.

Correlation between Exposure and Self-Efficacy in School Leadership

Table 3 presents the correlation between the level of exposure and self-efficacy in various aspects of school leadership among school leaders using Spearman rank correlation coefficient.

Table 3. Correlation of Level of Exposure and Self-Efficacy in School Leadership (N=1,900)

Variables	rs	p-value	Result	Decision on H0
Technical aspects	0.864	0.000	Significant	Reject
Organizing school events	0.872	0.000	Significant	Reject
Project implementation	0.867	0.000	Significant	Reject
Policy/program execution	0.833	0.000	Significant	Reject
Team building	0.821	0.000	Significant	Reject
Financial management	0.828	0.000	Significant	Reject
Time management	0.813	0.000	Significant	Reject
Mandated programs, projects and activities of SSG	0.825	0.000	Significant	Reject
Overall Result	0.902	0.000	Significant	Reject

The result indicates a strong positive correlation between the level of exposure and self-efficacy in various aspects of school leadership, with all correlation coefficients (rs) ranging from 0.813 to 0.902. The p-values for all variables are 0.000, which is less than the significance level of 0.05, indicating that the correlations are statistically significant.

Each specific aspect of school leadership, including technical aspects, organizing school events, project implementation, policy/program execution, team building, financial management, time management, and mandated programs, significantly correlates with self-efficacy. The highest correlation is observed in organizing school events (rs = 0.872), while the lowest is in time management (rs = 0.813). The overall correlation coefficient of 0.902 suggests a very strong relationship between the level of exposure and overall self-efficacy in school leadership.

The result corroborates with previous studies reporting that increasing student leadership self-efficacy beliefs directly affect leadership practices, highlighting the role of educational activities in enhancing these beliefs (Polatcan, 2023). Another study reported significant positive correlations between self-leadership and career self-efficacy in nursing students, further supporting that leadership experiences boost self-efficacy (Kawoun & Heakyung, 2018). Also, Villas (2019) found that senior high school students from public schools exhibited higher levels of self-efficacy in vicarious experiences compared to their counterparts in private schools, suggesting that the school environment plays a crucial role in developing leadership self-efficacy. These findings collectively indicate that exposure to leadership roles in school positively impacts self-efficacy in leading among students.

Conclusions

The study revealed a strong positive correlation between students' exposure to leadership activities and their self-efficacy in these roles, with the highest correlation observed in organizing school events and the lowest in time management. These findings suggest that increased exposure to leadership tasks significantly enhances students' confidence in their abilities, signifying the importance of providing frequent and varied leadership experiences in public schools.

Schools in SDO Bohol should develop comprehensive leadership training programs that cover a wide range of skills, including financial management and time management, to ensure students gain exposure and build confidence in all aspects of leadership.

Given the strong correlation between event organization and self-efficacy, schools should provide more opportunities for students to plan and manage school events to strengthen their confidence and leadership capabilities.

Schools should integrate leadership roles and responsibilities into the regular curriculum and extracurricular activities.

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